

EFFECTS OF TEST TEMPERATURE AND LOADING RATE ON THE FATIGUE AND FRACTURE RESISTANCE OF A CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED GLASS CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The response of a Nicalon/CAS continuous fibre reinforced glass ceramic matrix composite to both monotonic and cyclic loading has been studied at test temperatures of room temperature, 600, 800 and 1000°C in air. The flexural strength is strongly dependent on both the test temperature and nominal loading rate employed, and is observed to decrease with test temperature increase, and with nominal loading rate decrease. The fatigue endurance is also greatly reduced with test temperature increase. These results are discussed with reference to current theories of fibre-matrix interface structure.

Keywords: glass ceramic matrix composites, fracture, fatigue, elevated temperatures, loading rate

1. INTRODUCTION

Glass ceramic matrix composite materials have excellent potential for use in high temperature structural applications such as aero-engines⁽¹⁾. However, if materials are to be used in such applications, their response to both monotonic and cyclic loading must be studied in detail, at both ambient and elevated temperatures. The importance of test temperature and environment on the mechanical behaviour of glass ceramic matrix composite systems such as Nicalon/CAS⁽²⁾ and Nicalon/LAS⁽³⁾ has been extensively documented. In the as-received condition, a carbon interfacial layer (that develops during hot pressing) encourages fibre debonding and promotes toughness. However, when the interface becomes open to environmental ingress at elevated temperatures in air (for example in the presence of a matrix crack), the carbon interfacial layer may be replaced by a continuous silica layer that encourages fibre failure close to the plane of the crack, and thus promotes brittle composite behaviour. This reaction has been termed 'silica bridging'⁽⁴⁾.

Previous work^(2,5,6) has shown that a progressive failure mechanism occurs in a glass ceramic matrix composite when subjected to mechanical cyclic loading. Individual microcracks are observed to propagate under extended cyclic loading, and this may be rationalised if extended cyclic loading results in a decrease in bridging forces acting on the individual crack tips. Other studies⁽⁷⁾ have shown that, under cyclic loading, frictional sliding at the fibre-matrix interface may effect the value of the interfacial shear stress. Such observations suggest that the interfacial shear stress decreases under cyclic loading, and such decreases will cause less efficient load transfer to the bridging fibres. In addition, the density of cracking within specimens subjected to cyclic loading increases with increasing applied load cycles^(6,8), and this results in decreases in composite modulus⁽⁸⁾.

At a test temperature of 1000°C in air, it has been shown that specimens have similar lifetimes under both static and cyclic loading, and thus that failure is dominated primarily by static (maximum) applied stresses, even under cyclic loading⁽²⁾. However, at a test temperature of 800°C in air,

specimens loaded statically have considerably longer lifetimes than specimens loaded cyclically, and hence a cyclic effect is evident at this temperature⁽⁹⁾.

The aim of this paper is to illustrate the effect of test temperature on the response of a Nicalon/CAS continuous fibre reinforced glass ceramic matrix composite to both monotonic and cyclic loading. The effect of nominal loading rate on the flexural strength of the material is also studied over a range of test temperatures.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The system used in this study is a commercially available Nicalon/CAS continuous fibre reinforced glass ceramic matrix composite. All tests were performed on unidirectionally reinforced specimens containing a fibre volume fraction of 35%, and which were cut from two plates of material of dimensions 150x150mm², and of thicknesses 3.0 and 3.7mm, using diamond tooling. Monotonic ramps to failure and cyclic fatigue tests were performed.

All tests at room temperature, 800 and 1000°C were performed on specimens of depth 5mm and thickness 3.7mm, while tests performed at a test temperature of 600°C were performed on specimens of depth 5mm and thickness 3.0mm. Tests were carried out in three point bending with a total loading span of 40mm, and this corresponds to a total span to depth ratio of 8:1.

Monotonic ramps to failure were performed in order to determine the flexural strength of the material as a function of test temperature and nominal loading rate. All of these tests were performed on an Instron 8501 servohydraulic test machine. Cross head displacement rates of between 10⁻⁴ and 10mm/min were used. These correspond to nominal initial loading rates of between 0.12 and 3840MPa/min, as calculated from the nominal stress at the tensile surface during the initial linear section of the load-displacement traces.

Fatigue tests were carried out at temperatures of room temperature, 600 and 800°C in air. Tests performed at room temperature were performed on an Amsler Vibrophore electromagnetic resonance test machine at a test frequency of 50Hz and at an R-ratio of 0.1, where R is the ratio of minimum stress to maximum stress applied during the load cycle. In addition, a soft aluminium shim was placed between the specimen and roller on the compressive face of the bend bar to minimise contact damage. Fatigue tests performed at temperatures of 600 and 800°C were performed at an R-ratio of 0.1 and at a test frequency of 10Hz on an Instron 8501 servohydraulic test machine. In all cases, a maximum of 10⁶ cycles was applied.

After failure, specimens were gold coated and examined on a JEOL 6300 SEM operating at an accelerating voltage of 10kV.

3. RESULTS

Figure 1 shows a plot of flexural strength versus cross head displacement rate for the range of test temperatures studied. It can be seen that the flexural strength of the material is strongly dependent on both the test temperature and the cross head displacement rate employed. At any particular test temperature, increased flexural strengths are obtained at increased cross head displacement rates, although the effect of cross head displacement rate on flexural strength is more pronounced at 600 and 800°C than at the other two test temperatures. It can also be seen that at any particular cross head displacement rate, the flexural strength decreases markedly as temperature increases. Consider the data obtained at a cross head displacement rate of 10⁻¹mm/min. It can be seen that as temperature increases, the flexural strength of the material decreases, and that failure changes from "fibrous" at test temperatures of ≤600°C to "non-fibrous" at test temperatures of ≥800°C. For tests performed at a cross head displacement rate of 10⁻³mm/min, failures are "fibrous" at room temperature only (see Table 1).

Figures 2 (a and b) show SEM micrographs of a specimen that was ramped monotonically to failure at a test temperature of 600°C and at a cross head displacement rate of 10⁻¹mm/min. Damage consists of matrix cracking, fibre debonding and fibre pull out, and failures of this type are referred to

subsequently as 'fibrous' in nature. Figure 3a shows an SEM micrograph of a specimen ramped monotonically to failure at 600°C and at a cross head displacement rate of 10⁻³mm/min. Damage consists of initial mode I cracking and subsequent off axis cracking. No pull out is evident, and failures of this type are referred to as "non-fibrous" in nature. Figure 3b shows a higher magnification SEM micrograph of the initial mode I section of crack growth, and where no fibre pull out is observed. Table 1 illustrates the nature of failure in terms of test temperature and cross head displacement rate. All failures at room temperature were fibrous in nature, and all failures at a test temperature of 1000°C were non-fibrous over the range of loading rates employed here. However, at a test temperature of 600°C in air, non-fibrous failure occurs at a cross head displacement rate of 10⁻³ mm/min, but fibrous failure occurs at a cross head displacement rate of 10⁻¹ mm/min. At a test temperature of 800°C in air, non-fibrous failure results at a cross head displacement rate of 10⁻¹ mm/min, but fibrous failure results at a cross head displacement rate of 10mm/min. At the intermediate cross head displacement rate of 1mm/min, final failure contained initial mode I crack growth, and which exhibits no fibre pull out, but the areas of off axis cracking are bridged by fibres, and failure occurred by gross specimen collapse. Figure 4 shows schematic load-displacement plots for specimens ramped to failure that exhibit either a fibrous or a non-fibrous failure. Fibrous failure results from gross specimen collapse, whereas non-fibrous failure occurs in a more catastrophic manner.

Figure 5 shows a plot of number of cycles to failure versus applied peak stress for tests performed at temperatures of room temperature, 600 and 800°C.

The fatigue data produced at room temperature indicates that generally, specimens tested at high peak stress fail in fewer cycles than those tested at low peak stress. Failures occur only at peak stresses above the observed deviation from linearity in load-displacement traces (approximately 348MPa) but at stresses considerably lower than the flexural strength of the material. Failure under cyclic loading at room temperature was fibrous in nature, and occurred by gross specimen collapse. All specimens contained damage consisting of multiple matrix microcracking, even those that "ran out" to 10⁶ cycles.

The fatigue data produced at a test temperature of 600°C in air again indicates that specimens tested at high peak stress fail in fewer cycles than those tested at low peak stress. All failures at 600°C under cyclic loading were non-fibrous in nature, and occurred in a catastrophic manner. However, the specimen that ran out to 10⁶ cycles contained no damage.

At a test temperature of 800°C in air, failure under cyclic loading occurs rapidly, and within 2200 cycles for the load ranges studied here. Failures in all cases were both non-fibrous and catastrophic in nature.

4. DISCUSSION

Figure 1 indicates that the flexural strength of the Nicalon/CAS continuous fibre reinforced glass ceramic matrix composite is significantly effected by both test temperature and nominal loading rate. It appears that the flexural strength data can be divided into two distinct bands. These bands are indicative of the two distinct failure mechanisms. For non-fibrous failure, the maximum flexural strength is approximately 500MPa, while for fibrous failure the minimum flexural strength is approximately 600MPa. Clearly the change in failure mechanism can be controlled by test temperature and/or nominal loading rate.

The non-fibrous failures display no fibre pull out, see Figures 3a and 3b. In this system this has been shown to occur by a silica bridging mechanism⁽⁴⁾. Silica bridging will promote fibre failure on or close to the plane of the matrix crack in preference to fibre debonding, and ultimately fibre pull out. In this work it has been shown that such failures can occur at a low loading rate of 10⁻³mm/min and during cyclic fatigue at test temperatures as low as 600°C.

As stress is applied to the material, matrix cracking will occur, and cracks will increasingly tend to propagate into the specimen as stress levels are increased, even though fibres are bridging the crack. If a fibrous failure occurs, the rate at which matrix cracking propagates into the specimen is more

rapid than the rate at which fibre failure on the plane of the crack is promoted by silica bridge formation. Fibre debonding will consequently occur, and good strength will result. Alternatively, if a non-fibrous failure results, the rate at which on axis fibre failure is induced in the wake of the matrix crack due to silica bridge formation is greater than the rate at which matrix cracks propagate. Fibre failure would cause increases in crack tip stress intensity, and would therefore promote further crack propagation. Eventual catastrophic failure would result, and this would produce a low flexural strength. It is apparent therefore that the kinetics of the silica bridging mechanism relative to the progression of cracks under increased stress into the specimen will dictate whether or not a sufficient degree of on-axis fibre failure will occur to give a non-fibrous failure, prior to gross specimen collapse. It is important to note that the ingress of oxygen to fibre-matrix interfaces requires matrix cracking to occur.

The explanation for the most marked influence of loading rate at the test temperatures of 600 and 800°C is simply that within the range of cross head displacement rates employed, it is at these test temperatures that a transition in failure mechanism is observed. It is possible that even at 1000°C at a sufficiently high loading rate that a fibrous failure might result.

It is of interest to note that there are clear effects of loading rate even at test temperatures when only a single failure mechanism operates. So at a test temperature of 1000°C, once again the nominal loading rate is faster and less time is available for silica bridge formation (the total time of tests at a temperature of 1000°C ranges from several hours to a matter of seconds for the range employed here). More intriguing is the observation of an effect of loading rate at room temperature. The reason for this is not entirely clear and requires further investigation, but it is plausible that an environmental effect is responsible. Monolithic glasses and glass ceramics are often susceptible to static fatigue^(10,11), and thus the measured (matrix) strength may depend upon the loading rate employed⁽¹⁰⁾. Such observations are often rationalised by a stress corrosion cracking mechanism involving both an attacking species (usually atmospheric water) and an applied (crack tip) stress. However it is thought that the presence of fibres in this composite system would minimise such an effect. Indeed the fracture toughness of the matrix is very low (approximately 1MPa√m), whereas the nominal toughness of the composite is much higher (approximately 30MPa√m, as measured using chevron notched specimens⁽²⁾). Nevertheless, an effect has been observed and flexural strength tests will be performed in vacuum to investigate the failure mechanism further.

Figure 5 shows that the response of the material to cyclic loading is also strongly effected by test temperature. At room temperature, specimens tested at high peak stresses fail in fewer cycles than those tested at low peak stresses. The form of the data is indicative of a progressive failure mechanism, and this has been elucidated in previous work^(2,5,6,9). During cyclic loading, the value of the interfacial shear stress decreases⁽⁷⁾, and this reduces the efficiency of load transfer from the matrix to the fibres. Thus the bridging forces on microcracks decrease, and microcrack propagation is promoted. In this study, at a test temperature of 600°C, the form of the fatigue data indicates that a progressive failure mechanism again operates, where specimens cycled at a high peak stress have a lower lifetime than those cycled at a low peak stress. However, a non-fibrous failure mode occurs at 600°C, whereas a fibrous failure mode is obtained at room temperature. In addition, previous work has indicated that a cyclic effect exists at 800°C when non-fibrous failure also results.

The three sets of fatigue data are displaced from each other, and it can be said that as test temperature is increased, the fatigue performance of the material is reduced considerably. This is plausibly again due to the rate of silica bridge formation relative to the growth of fatigue cracks. It is apparent that as non-fibrous failure occurs at test temperatures of 600 and 800°C under cyclic loading, interface structure is effecting the fatigue performance of the material. At a test temperature of 600°C, it appears that the interface structure allows a progressive failure mechanism to operate in a manner similar to that at room temperature, but that during the test, silica bridging may occur and result in non-fibrous failure and poorer fatigue life than that at room temperature. Similar comments are applicable to tests performed under cyclic loading at the test temperature of 800°C. Therefore, it is apparent that the rate of silica bridge formation may control the nature of failure in the Nicalon/CAS material under both monotonic and cyclic loading.

In general, such observations indicate that marked effects of cyclic frequency must be expected in such materials. If rate constants for the silica bridging reaction can be established, it should be

possible to predict the reduction in cyclic frequency required to collapse the fatigue data obtained at a test temperature of 600°C to that obtained at 800°C. Based on observations reported in this paper, it will be difficult to use these composites at operating temperatures of greater than 600°C, if they are to be subjected to significant tensile loading.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The flexural strength of the Nicalon/CAS continuous fibre reinforced glass ceramic matrix composite is strongly dependent on test temperature and nominal loading rate. Flexural strength is reduced as the test temperature is increased and as the cross head displacement rate is decreased. The effect of loading rate is most prominent at 600 and 800°C, and this is deduced to be due to the rate of silica bridge formation at the fibre matrix interface. Such observations promote fibre failure close to the crack plane and no fibre pull out is observed.

The fatigue performance of the material is also strongly dependent on test temperature, and is reduced as test temperature is increased. This is again thought to be due to the rate of silica bridge formation at the fibre matrix interface. Progressive failure occurs under extended cyclic loading at test temperatures of room temperature and 600°C, and the experimental observations indicate that test frequency may also influence the fatigue endurance of the material strongly.

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CHDR mm/min \ T(°C)	20	600	800	1000
10 ⁻⁴				Non Fibrous
10 ⁻³	Fibrous	Non Fibrous	Non Fibrous	Non Fibrous
10 ⁻²		Non Fibrous		Non Fibrous
10 ⁻¹	Fibrous	Fibrous	Non Fibrous	Non Fibrous
0.5				Non Fibrous
1			Mixed	
10		Fibrous	Fibrous	

Table 1. Failure mechanism as a function of test temperature and cross head displacement rate.

Figure 1. A plot of cross head displacement rate versus flexural strength for specimens tested at temperatures of room temperature, 600, 800 and 1000°C.

Figures 2a and 2b. SEM micrographs of a specimen ramped monotonically to failure at a test temperature of 600°C and a cross head displacement rate of 10^{-3} mm/min showing a) fibrous failure and b) fibre debonding and pull out

Figures 3a and 3b. SEM micrographs of a specimen ramped monotonically to failure at a test temperature of 600°C and a cross head displacement rate of 0.1mm/min showing a) a non-fibrous failure and b) no pull out in the initial mode I crack growth section.

Figure 4. A schematic diagram showing representative load-displacement traces for both fibrous and non-fibrous failures.

Figure 5. A plot of number of applied load cycles versus peak stress for specimens cyclically loaded at test temperatures of room temperature, 600 and 800°C